

**YOUTH IN THE GLORIFICATION OF HUMAN DIGNITY
DEVELOPMENT OF LEGAL SPIRITUALITY.**

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Abstract. When we reflect on the changes that have occurred in the life of the country, we witness that in the fertile ground of independence, the value of human being is glorified in our country, especially we are creating wide opportunities for young people, and we are focused on ensuring human rights and freedoms. There is great wisdom in the saying of our grandfather Amir Temur, "Where there is rule of law, there is freedom." This wisdom has its own meaning even now.

Keywords: "a society where human dignity is a priority, a people-loving state, "For human dignity".

As you know, in the reforms carried out within the framework of the strategy of action in the Republic of independent Uzbekistan, issues such as the problem of youth, raising and developing the legal spirituality of youth in honor of human dignity, increasing the intellectual potential of young people have been raised to the level of Public Policy. In particular, it should be noted that organizational and legal and social conditions are being created in order to develop the legal spirituality of young people in honor of human dignity in our country. It is no secret to anyone that the foundation "our youth future", the youth club, the School of young entrepreneurs, the School of Temurbeks, the presidential School, the schools of creativity, the Youth Library, the young reader competition, the organization of youth leaders in the neighborhoods are also promoted in five important initiatives to develop the legal spirituality of young people and

As everyone knows, a person has been living in a family environment since his birth. In our masterpieces such as "Qurani Karim" and Hadith about family holiness, raising children, "Qobusnoma", "Shahname", "Baburnoma", "Temurnoma", "Gulistan", which are considered the spiritual heritage of our ancestors, it is once again assured that upbringing is an important factor in the development of youth spirituality, especially in the glorification of human value. Even the founder of a centralized state, Amir Timur, noted that "I also made sure

that in raising children, a deeper wisdom is needed than public administration.” And it is not for nothing that Abdullah Alwani in his work “Turkic Gulistan or morality” says that “upbringing is for us either a life - or a mammoth, or salvation - or a matter of destruction, or bliss - or a matter of disaster.”

It is known that the family is the basis of every society, the basis, and in youth, humanism, hard work, morality, patriotism and high feelings are absorbed, first of all, in the family environment. This process is carried out through the step of the grandfathers, the sign of the father, the love of the mother. The importance of the family for the development of the legal spirituality of young people in the glorification of human dignity is great. In vain, they did not say that “the bird does what it sees in the nest.” Because, first of all, the child receives upbringing in the family.

As a result of comprehensive reforms and creative work carried out in our country, the consciousness of young people, the formation, thinking, worldview of their legal spirituality are changing. In the establishment of a legal state, civil society in the country, the importance of the idea that “from national recovery-towards national growth” is growing. Despite the important work carried out in this regard, in the process of updates in the social, economic and political spheres, large-scale work is being carried out in order to increase the effectiveness of legal spiritual development of youth, educational reforms.

All countries in the world are trying to build a civil society. Civil society is a social system in which human rights and freedoms decide in the formation of the legal spirituality of young people in the mastery of law, the glorification of human dignity. The construction of this society means the transition from a strong state to a strong society, its gradual implementation. One of the conditions of a Democratic state and civil society that is being built in the country is the presence of laws that serve to ensure their decent living, especially at present, the development of the legal spirituality of young people in the glorification of human dignity. Acquaintance with the essence of their content and compliance with laws is a civil duty, which is manifested in the development of legal spirituality of young people, increasing their legal consciousness and legal knowledge.

It should be said that the media are currently making a significant contribution to the development and elevation of their legal spirituality among young people in the glorification of human dignity. On the web Lex.uz the services of his site are pleasing to everyone. Information on all regulatory documents is regularly provided in it. On television, which quickly penetrates

into each family, the activities of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis show a series of testimony about the comments of Deputies on laws, the content of certain articles of the Constitution and laws, elections. All existing newspapers, magazines have a great focus on providing legal knowledge. Regular articles about the Constitution and laws, legal advice, guidance, questions and answers on the legal topic are vivid evidence of our opinion. In particular, about 20 newspapers and magazines such as “Justice”, “lawyer”, “Law and duty”, “civil society”, “in the world of law”, “in the post” on the topic of human dignity are given advice, guidance and their legal knowledge in order to develop the legal spirituality of young people, to instill the content of legal relations, laws.

Based on the requirements of the time, in subsequent years, a new state policy on youth was introduced in the country. Article 10 of the Law No. 406 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on state youth policy”, adopted on September 14, 2016, imposes on educational institutions a number of tasks, in particular, the responsibility to keep young people from becoming criminals, to develop the legal spirituality of young people. Indeed, it is a pity that a child who has been educated at school for 11 years remains a criminal.

Thanks to independence, the Uzbek people of Erksevar acquired their own land, their own language, their own religion. It is necessary to enjoy values and spiritual heritage in order to develop the legal spirituality of young people in order to restore national pride and honor and now honor human dignity. Independence and spirituality are very related concepts. Spirituality cannot be enslaved by a great people, kept under the oppression of eternal desire. In order for such spirituality to mature, be absorbed into souls, it will also be necessary to strengthen independence. The future of the Almighty arises on the basis of a great state, great social, economic reforms, powerful spirituality. On the basis of the development of legal spirituality in order to glorify the human value of each age, a democratic legal state is built through the spiritual maturity of the entire nation. State leader Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev has always paid great attention to spirituality and enlightenment. Thanks to this rational policy, young people recognize their legal spirituality and identity, perceive their spirituality and realize their functions before history.

Without the development of the legal spirituality of the representatives of the younger generation in order to glorify the human value, it is difficult to achieve success in the growth of the people's life and marriage, as well as in the development of the country. At the first stage of reforms, the goal pursued for the development of the legal spirituality of young people is fully

realized. At the second stage, the ground is prepared for the tasks that need to be carried out. Indeed, only thanks to thoughtful and perfect thinking of representatives of the spiritually free, free younger generation, great achievements can be achieved in every area. In other words, only legal spiritual youth in the glorification of human dignity can be ready for the reforms of a strong society.

Today there are various answers to the question "What is spirituality". Especially since 1997, in connection with the beginning of the teaching of the subject "fundamentals of spirituality" in all universities in the country, everyone's attention to this topic has grown even more. Spirituality is associated with the psyche of a person. Including the psyche of young people, of course, changes as a result of external influences. The economic situation, place and position of a person in society do not affect his spirituality. But, nevertheless, spirituality has its own independent direction. For example, we are mistaken in both judgments when we say that the richer a person is, the darker he is, the higher his spiritual maturity, or, conversely, lower. Scholars such as Alisher Navoi, Mahdumi Azam, Khoja Ahrori Valiy have become spiritually competent, as well as very wealthy. Many such examples can be cited.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the work on the development of the legal spirituality of young people in the glorification of human value in spite of the numerous decrees, decisions and laws issued in mamalakat cannot be considered at the level of demand. First of all, in each school it is necessary to provide young people with a specialist in the field of law in order to develop legal spirituality, to know rights and laws. If a specialist takes a law class, the effectiveness of obtaining legal knowledge will be higher. In higher educational institutions, questions of the quiz on Constitutional Law, Civil Law, Environmental Law, Land Law, agrarian law, Family Law, Administrative Law, Financial Law, Criminal Law, cocktail Law, Civil Procedure Law, Criminal Procedure Law, international law should be written, thereby raising the legal educational development of young people. Ending with reflections on the role and importance of the development of legal spirituality in youth in the glorification of human dignity, first of all, it should be understood in depth that achieving the development of legal spirituality for representatives of the younger generation is not a one-year or ten - year work. Hulk, the nation develops and enriches its national spirituality over the years, centuries. Because spirituality is not the sum of hardened dogmas, but rather a continuous process in constant movement, and as progress continues, due to its intense

development, the requirements for the development of youth legal spirituality in the glorification of human value also appear fanatically. As the country steps from the development stage to new heights, this time should accelerate rapidly and, naturally, the development of the legal spirituality of young people should be able to preserve and preserve the healthy future of society and the nation. So, in the construction of national statehood and democratic society, in harmony with universal values, forming a sense of respect for national values and honoring human dignity, in order to develop the legal enlightenment of young people, as well as in the implementation of such an important task as strengthening their historical consciousness with a priority worldview, the appeal to the heritage of Young people should evaluate history objectively and truthfully, contribute to the enrichment and development of spiritual heritage, and on this basis be worthy and able in every possible way to such a great task as to gain the heights of today's World Science and culture.

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